

Studies on Some Formylcoumarins

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The syntheses of some β -coumarinyl acrylic acids, β -coumarinyl alanines and chromonyl coumarins from 6-formyl- and 7-formyl coumarin and their 4-methyl derivatives have been described.

IN the course of some other work, we prepared 7-formyl- and 7-formyl-4-methylcoumarin¹ and the present work deals with the exploration of further synthetic possibilities of these formyl coumarins and also of 6-formyl- and 6-formyl-4-methylcoumarin which have been obtained from 6-bromo-methyl- and 6-bromo methyl-4-methylcoumarin by heating with hexamine in acetic acid. These coumarins on Perkin acetylation with fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride gave the corresponding β -coumarinyl acrylic acids. They decolourised bromine water and potassium permanganate solution. In a further study, the synthesis of α -amino acids with coumarinyl units has been carried out. 7-Formyl-, 7-formyl-4-methyl- and 6-formyl-4-methylcoumarin were condensed with hippuric acid in the presence of acetic anhydride and sodium acetate and the intermediate oxazolone derivatives formed were converted into β -(7-coumarinyl) alanine (Ia), β -(4-methyl-7-coumarinyl) alanine (Ib) and β -(4-methyl-6-coumarinyl) alanine (II) respectively, by heating with red phosphorus and hydriodic acid. They all gave a positive ninhydrin test and were soluble in sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid.

With a view to synthesise chromones with a coumarinyl group in 2-position which do not appear to have been synthesised so far, 7-formyl-, 7-formyl-4-methyl-, 6-formyl- and 6-formyl-4-methylcoumarin were condensed with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide when coumarinyl vinyl *o*-hydroxyphenyl ketones were obtained. These compounds gave a brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride, a red colour with con. sulphuric acid and a positive Wilson test. They gave an acetyl derivative indicating the presence of a free hydroxyl group. Cyclization by refluxing with selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol gave 7-(2'-chromonyl) coumarin (IIIa), 4-methyl-7-(2'-chromonyl) coumarin (IIIb), 6-(2'-chromonyl) coumarin (IVa) and 4-methyl-6-(2'-chromonyl) coumarin (IVb).

Experimental

6-Formylcoumarin : 6-Bromomethylcoumarin² (2 g.) was refluxed with hexamine (5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Hydrochloric acid (1 : 1; 20 ml.) was then added and the heating continued

for further 15 min. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in cold water crystallised from acetic acid in white plates (0.8 g.), m.p. 189°. Sen and Chakravarti³ who prepared it by a different method gave the same m.p.

4-Methyl-6-formylcoumarin : Obtained as above from 4-methyl-6-bromomethylcoumarin² (1 g.) and crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles (0.5 g.) gave m.p. 211°. (Found : C, 70.18; H, 4.37. $C_{11}H_8O_3$ requires C, 70.21; H, 4.24%).

The 2,4-D.N.P. : Prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene in orange needles, m.p. 322°. (Found : N, 15.34. $C_{17}H_{12}O_6N_4$ requires N, 15.23%).

β -(7-Coumarinyl) acrylic acid : 7-Formylcoumarin¹ (0.5 g.) was heated at 170°-80° for 12 hr. with sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and the reaction mixture poured in cold water. The solid obtained crystallised from acetic acid in yellow cubes (0.3 g.), m.p. 275°. (Found : C, 66.58; H, 3.72. $C_{12}H_8O_4$ requires C, 66.67; H, 3.70%).

β -(4-Methyl-7-coumarinyl) acrylic acid : Prepared as above from 4-methyl-7-formylcoumarin (0.8 g.) and crystallised from acetic acid in white needles gave m.p. 315°. (Found : C, 67.41; H, 4.25. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 67.82; H, 4.34%).

β -(6-Coumarinyl) acrylic acid : Prepared from 6-formylcoumarin (1 g.) as above and crystallised from acetic acid in white needles (0.7 g.) gave m.p. 306°. (Found : C, 66.40; H, 3.91. $C_{12}H_8O_4$ requires C, 66.67; H, 3.70%).

β -(4-Methyl-6-coumarinyl) acrylic acid : Prepared from 4-methyl-6-formylcoumarin (0.5 g.) as above and crystallised from acetic acid in needles (0.2 g.) gave m.p. 303°. (Found : C, 67.66; H, 4.11. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 67.82; H, 4.34%).

4-(7'-Coumarinal) 2-phenyl-5-oxazolone : 7-Formylcoumarin (2 g.) was warmed with hippuric acid (4 g.) fused sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 ml.) till a clear solution was formed. This was then refluxed for 1 hr. and then cooled. Alcohol (20 ml.) was added. The yellow solid which separated

on cooling was washed with boiling water and cold alcohol. It crystallised from nitrobenzene in yellow plates (2 g.), m.p. 230°. (Found : C, 71.55; H, 3.55; N, 4.53. $C_{19}H_{12}O_4N$ requires C, 71.69; H, 3.77; N, 4.40%.)

hippuric acid (2 g.), fused sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (15 ml.) as before and crystallised from nitrobenzene in yellow needles (0.9 g.) gave m.p. 241°. (Found : C, 72.40; H, 3.59; N, 3.98. $C_{20}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 72.51; H, 3.92; N, 4.23%.)

β-(7-Coumarinyl) alanine : The above oxazolone derivative (1.5 g.) was heated under reflux with red phosphorus (1.2 g.), acetic anhydride (7 ml.) and hydriodic acid (5 ml.; 50%), for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered and cooled and the product obtained was dissolved in water and neutralised with ammonium hydroxide solution. The product obtained on concentration of the solution crystallised from water in white needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 280°. (Found : C, 61.45; H, 4.66; N, 5.50. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 61.80; H, 4.72; N, 6.00%.)

4-(4'-Methyl-7'-coumarinal) 2-phenyl-5-oxazolone : Prepared as before from 4-methyl-7-formylcoumarin (2 g.), hippuric acid (4 g.), fused sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (15 ml.) and crystallised from nitrobenzene in yellow needles (0.8 g.) gave m.p. 263°. (Found : C, 72.10; H, 3.99; N, 4.55. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4N$ requires C, 72.51; H, 3.92; N, 4.23%.)

β-(4-Methyl-7-coumarinyl) alanine : - Prepared from the above oxazolone derivative as before and crystallised from water in tiny white needles (0.4 g.) gave m.p. 255°. (Found : C, 62.78; H, 5.48; N, 5.79. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 63.15; H, 5.26; N, 5.68%.)

4(4'-Methyl-6'-coumarinal) 2-phenyl-5-oxazolone : Prepared from 4-methyl-6-formylcoumarin (1 g.),

β-(4-Methyl-6-coumarinyl) alanine : It was prepared by refluxing the above oxazolone (1.0 g.) with red phosphorus (0.8 g.) and hydriodic acid (5 ml.; 50%) in acetic anhydride (5 ml.) for 3 hr. The product obtained on working up the reaction mixture as before separated from water as white granules (0.4 g.), m.p. 247°-50°. (Found : C, 62.86; H, 5.55; N, 5.51. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 63.15; H, 5.26; N, 5.66%.)

β-(4-Methyl-7-coumarinyl) vinyl-*o*-hydroxyphenylketone : A mixture of 4-methyl-7-formylcoumarin (1 g.) in alcohol, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (0.7 g.) and potassium hydroxide (10 g. in 10 ml. water) was kept for 24 hr. and then diluted with water and acidified. The precipitated yellow product was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from acetic acid in dark yellow needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 214°. (Found : C, 74.71; H, 4.80. $C_{19}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 74.50; H, 4.57%.)

The acetyl derivative : Prepared by heating the above ketone (0.5 g.) with fused sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.) for 2 hr. and crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow needles gave m.p. 156°. (Found : C, 72.06; H, 4.52. $C_{21}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 72.40; H, 4.59%.)

4-Methyl-7-(2'-chromonyl) coumarin: The above hydroxy ketone (0.5 g.) dissolved in isoamyl alcohol (50 ml.) was mixed with selenium dioxide (1.25 g.) and refluxed at 140°-50° for 24 hr. The solution was filtered hot and the product obtained on cooling crystallised from nitrobenzene in pale yellow cubes, m.p. 262°. (Found: C, 75.09; H, 3.79. $C_{19}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 74.99; H, 3.94%).

β -(7-Coumarinyl) vinyl-*o*-hydroxyphenyl ketone: It was prepared by keeping a mixture of 7-formyl-coumarin (1 g.) and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (2 ml.) in alcohol (25 ml.) with potassium hydroxide (10 g. in 10 ml. water) for 24 hr. and working up as before. It crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 204°-06°. (Found: C, 74.37; H, 3.94. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 73.98; H, 4.11%).

The acetyl derivative: Prepared as usual and crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow shining plates gave m.p. 130°. (Found: C, 71.81; H, 4.26. $C_{20}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 71.86; H, 4.19%).

7-(2'-Chromonyl) coumarin: The above ketone (0.8 g.) in isoamyl alcohol (50 ml.) was refluxed with selenium dioxide (2 g.) at 140°-50° for 24 hr. The product obtained on working up as before crystallised from dilute acetic acid in pale yellow needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 250°. (Found: C, 74.09; H, 3.12. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 74.49; H, 3.44%).

β -(6-Coumarinyl) vinyl-*o*-hydroxyphenyl ketone: Prepared by keeping a mixture of 6-formyl coumarin (2 g.) in alcohol with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (4 ml.) and potassium hydroxide (20 ml.; 100%) for 24 hr. and working up as before. Crystallised from acetic acid in yellow plates (0.8 g.), m.p. 218°. (Found: C, 74.24; H, 4.25. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 73.98; H, 4.11%).

The acetyl derivative: Prepared from the above ketone as usual and crystallised from dilute alcohol in light yellow shining prisms gave m.p. 157°.

(Found: C, 71.64; H, 4.43. $C_{20}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 71.86; H, 4.19%).

6-(2'-Chromonyl) coumarin: The above hydroxy ketone (0.6 g.) was refluxed in isoamyl alcohol with selenium dioxide (2 g.) at 145°-50° for 24 hr. The product obtained on working up as before crystallised from acetic acid in brown needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 260°. (Found: C, 74.67; H, 3.31. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 74.49; H, 3.44%).

β -(4-Methyl-6-coumarinyl) vinyl-*o*-hydroxyphenyl ketone: Prepared as before from 4-methyl-6-formyl coumarin (1 g.) and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (0.7 g.) and potassium hydroxide (10 g. in 10 ml. water) as before and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (0.5 g.) gave m.p. 218°. (Found: C, 74.69; H, 4.41. $C_{19}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 74.50; H, 4.57%).

The acetyl derivative: Prepared as usual and crystallised from dilute alcohol in light yellow plates, m.p. 151°. (Found: C, 72.69; H, 4.59. $C_{21}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 72.41; H, 4.59%).

4-Methyl-6-(2'-chromonyl) coumarin: Obtained from the above hydroxyketone (1 g.) by refluxing in boiling isoamyl alcohol with selenium dioxide for 24 hrs. and crystallised from acetic acid in tiny white needles (0.4 g.) gave m.p. 300°. (Found: C, 74.80; H, 3.91. $C_{19}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 74.99; H, 3.94%).

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